

**Supplements for Fault Friction Derived from Fault Bend Influence on Coseismic Slip
During the 2019 Ridgecrest M_w 7.1 Mainshock****Authors:** Milliner, C.W.D.^{1*}, Aati, S.¹, Avouac, J.P.¹¹ California Institute of Technology, Pasadena, CA**Contents of this file**

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Overview

Here the supplementary figures we provide further details on how the magnitude of the maximum differential stress is estimated (section S1), describe how SH_{\max} is measured from surface fracture (S2) and shows the displacement measurements, validation of stress model, data misfit and a synthetic resolution test. Metadata for the satellites images used in this study are listed in Table S1.

S1. Magnitude of Maximum Differential Stress

To calculate the magnitude of the maximum shear stresses (also equal to half the differential stress), $\Delta\sigma = [\sigma_1 - \sigma_3]/2$, we use the stress rotation ($\Delta\theta$) following the approach of Hardebeck & Hauksson (2001). The stress rotations are measured by comparing our co-seismic stress tensor to the postseismic stress tensor inferred from focal mechanisms of aftershocks (Sheng and Meng, 2020; Hauksson and Jones, 2020; Wang and Zhan, 2020; Hardebeck, 2020). This calculation also requires knowledge of the stress drop ($\Delta\tau = 1.86$ MPa for the northern zone, $\Delta\tau = 4.3$ MPa for the central zone and $\Delta\tau = 1.24$ MPa for the southern zone) that we use from an estimated derived from a finite fault slip model (Wang et al., 2020). Lastly it requires the angle between the fault (measured from our optical displacement maps) and our estimated $SH_{\max}(\theta)$. These values can then be used to estimate $\Delta\sigma$ with the following relation of Hardebeck & Hauksson (2001),

$$\tan\Delta\theta = \frac{1 - \frac{\Delta\tau}{\Delta\sigma} \sin 2\theta - \sqrt{\left(\frac{\Delta\tau}{\Delta\sigma}\right)^2 + 1 - 2 \frac{\Delta\tau}{\Delta\sigma} \sin 2\theta}}{\frac{\Delta\tau}{\Delta\sigma} \cos 2\theta}. \quad \text{S1}$$

S2. SH_{\max} measurements from surface fractures

To measure the horizontal direction of maximum compressive stress (SH_{\max}) we use the relative orientation of different fractures, namely Riedel (R), conjugate Riedel (R') and through-going shear (Y). These fractures were mapped in high-detail by field geologists in the days-weeks following the 2019 Ridgecrest event and with high-resolution aerial and uncrewed aerial vehicle imagery (< 2-20 cm resolution) (Ponti et al., 2020; Rodriguez Padilla et al., 2020). The SH_{\max} is measured from two types of sets of fractures. The first is from the orientation of R-Y shears and the other are the orientations of R'-Y. For a set of R-Y fractures, there are typically multiple en-echelon R fractures, where we measure the orientation of each R fracture and take their average. To then measure the orientation of the through-going Y shear we estimate the average fault trace that transects through the R shears and is consistent with the strike of the rupture at a larger ~ 100 m scale (e.g., see Fig. S4c). From this we estimate SH_{\max} as 45 deg. from the Y-shears. From knowledge of the angle between Y-R fractures this gives us the internal angle of friction which is on average $\sim 20^\circ$.

To measure SH_{\max} from the R'-Y fracture sets we first identify the R'. The R' is identified from either the high angular obliquity of the suspected R' to the throughgoing Y shear and/or due to the opposite stepping of the en-echelon fracturing compared to the Y shear, which indicates slip along a conjugate and antithetic fault. The SH_{\max} is then estimated from knowledge of the internal friction angle (derived from the average value estimated from the Y-R fracture sets) and estimating the bisector angle between the expected R orientation and R'.

In total for the R-Y fractures sets we measured 280 synthetic Riedel shears and 63 Y shears. While for the R'-Y fracture sets we measured 15 R' and Y shears. We find that the median angular misfit between the SH_{\max} direction measured from the orientation of fractures and our coseismic slip vector with a single domain that extends across the entire rupture is $10.3 \pm 13.2^\circ$. However, a stress model that separates the coseismic slip vectors into three domains (the results of which are shown in the maintext) yields a factor of ~ 3 improvement of the median fit to the independent estimate of SH_{\max} from the fracture orientations (with an median angular misfit of $3.7 \pm 12.4^\circ$). This improvement of the fit of a multi-domain coseismic stress that allows for along-strike variability with the independent SH_{\max} estimates from the Riedel fractures supports our choice of partitioning our stress model into three domains. However we note that we cannot justify dividing the stress model into four domains as we lose sufficient diversity in the orientation of slip vectors within each zone to reliably recover the stress state.

Fig. S1. 3D Optical Displacement maps (a-c) and coseismic slip vectors (c). (a-c) shows the east-west, vertical and north-south displacement maps, respectively, from image correlation of WorldView 1-3 imagery and SPOT-6. c) Compares the observed and model prediction slip vectors in black and green (overlain), respectively. Dashed boxes correspond to the three stress zones

Fig. S2. (a) Map of view for the slip rakes used in the inversion for stress. b-d) shows coseismic slip measured from our optical displacement maps in the fault-perpendicular direction (upper right) and vertical (bottom right) directions. Slip measured in the fault-parallel direction is shown in Fig. 3a and b.

Figure S3. a) shows along-fault slip profile for fault parallel component of slip compared to measurements from other studies for the M_w 7.1 mainshock event. b) comparison of fault-parallel displacement measured by Gold et al. (2020) with fault displacements measured here. c) slip profile along the foreshock rupture (shown as negative values in Fig. 1b)

Figure S4. Results of synthetic resolution test assessing ability to recover a known stress state. The resolution test attempts to recover the stress model of Hardebeck (2020) (red symbols), with our inverted synthetic result shown by green symbols, which agree well within the uncertainties (colored regions). Top left shows southern zone, top right northern zone and bottom left shows central zone. Bottom right shows the distribution of the stress shape ratio (R) where the binned histogram values are from our inversion derived from a bootstrap of the synthetic slip vectors, while vertical lines show the known mean R values of Hardebeck (2020) and colored regions show the 95% confidence regions, showing very good recovery of the stress shape ratio for each zone.

Fig. S5. Lower hemisphere projection showing the orientations of the principal stresses for the single zone, homogenous stress model (s1 is green circle, s2 is green cross and s2 is green + sign). The colored regions show the probability densities for the principal directions estimated from bootstrapping the original slip vector data.

σ_1 σ_2 σ_3
 ○ × + This study

Fig. S6. Lower hemisphere projection showing the orientations of the principal stresses for the two-zone zone (s1 is green circle, s2 is green cross and s2 is green + sign) separated at latitude 35.73°N. The colored regions show the probability densities for the principal directions estimated from bootstrapping the original slip vector data. Top shows the stress state of the northern half of the rupture and bottom plot the southern half.

Fig. S7. Distributions for the SH_{\max} (top row, a-c), maximum shear stress ($\Delta\sigma$, second row, d-f) and frictional coefficients and stress drop (bottom row, g-i). a-c) The distribution of SH_{\max} is derived from the bootstrap sample of our stress tensors from inverting the slip vectors for each of the three stress zones (labeled in the plot title). The dashed black lines show the 1σ and the red lines the post- SH_{\max} from studies using aftershock focal mechanisms (Hauksson and Jones, 2020; Sheng and Meng, 2020; Wang and Zhan, 2020). D-f) The uncertainties from SH_{\max} are then propagated through to estimate the distribution of the deviatoric stresses for each zone. The red line shows the sample mean reported in the maintext. G-i) shows the distribution for the static friction (g), dynamic friction. (h) and stress drop (i) for the central zone, where the variability is derived from the variability in $\Delta\sigma$.

Figure S8. Plot of stress state of northern zone with displacement points and slip magnitude (colored dots). Failure envelopes of static and dynamic friction are those derived from the central zone. Absolute stress magnitudes for the northern zone shown above are estimated by assuming σ_2 is the same as that found within the central zone, because it is vertically orientated, and follows a depth-dependent effective stress profile assuming hydrostatic pore pressure.

Fig. S9. Plots illustrating the agreement between the observed slip vector and slip predicted by the background stress model of Hardebeck (2020) when projected onto the ruptured faults. Plots are separated for each component of the slip direction. Top from left to right shows the East, North and Vertical component of motion. Red dashed line shows the 1:1 line, with the annotation stating the p-value for a null hypothesis of a model with gradient of zero and the Pearson correlation coefficient characterizing the strength of correlation. Bottom shows a histogram of the angular difference in the slip rake between the observed and predicted slip vector of the background stress model (Hardebeck, 2020).

Table S 1. This table lists the metadata of the optical satellite images used to generate the 3D displacement maps. Column 1 refers to the image ID. Column 2 the date of acquisition. Column the time of acquisition. GSD = ground sampling distance in meters. Cov = percent of the image footprint that covers the rupture.

ID	Date	Time	Off-Nadir Angle	Platform	GSD (m)	Cov(%)) Mw.7.1	Cov(%) MW.6.4
Pre-Event							
A010014C7D553500	7/23/2016	18:27:48	24.7	WV02	0.554	17.841	78.934
A010014C7D554800	7/23/2016	18:27:47	24.1	WV02	0.549	11.276	46.808
A010014C7D55E600	7/31/2016	18:31:29	25.4	WV02	0.56	4.176	61.479
A010014C7D55F100	7/31/2016	18:31:28	25.3	WV02	0.559	23.654	0
A010014C7D560400	7/31/2016	18:31:27	25.2	WV02	0.558	16.349	0
A010014C7D55F900	7/31/2016	18:31:30	25.5	WV02	0.561	0	17.024
A010014C7D3DE800	9/8/2016	18:55:34	18.3	WV03	0.337	5.596	27.256
A010014C7D3DF700	9/8/2016	18:55:37	18	WV03	0.337	0.452	0
A010014C7D557D00	9/8/2016	18:55:21	25.7	WV03	0.371	30.095	0
A010014C7D555300	9/8/2016	18:55:20	27.1	WV03	0.379	24.966	26.462
A010014C7D556E00	9/8/2016	18:55:18	28.5	WV03	0.388	2.575	100
A010014C7D556800	9/8/2016	18:55:23	24.3	WV03	0.364	2.532	0
A010014C7D3DC100	9/8/2016	18:55:36	18.1	WV03	0.337	15.263	45.124
A010014CB0200100	9/26/2016	18:47:42	28	WV03	0.384	0	21.67
A010014CB00E8E00	9/26/2016	18:48:34	29	WV03	0.393	0	17.857
A010014CB01D6800	10/15/2016	18:56:00	21.4	WV03	0.35	0	1.502
A010014CB01D8400	10/15/2016	18:55:01	20.9	WV03	0.348	0	2.866
A010014CB01CCB00	10/21/2016	18:53:07	22	WV03	0.353	0	4.536

A010014CB01CDF00	10/21/2016	18:52:07	26.9	WV03	0.378	0	13.618
2020014C7D55FE00	11/18/2016	21:43:37	10.1	WV01	0.513	4.333	30.279
2020014C7D55D700	11/18/2016	21:43:36	10.5	WV01	0.514	21.377	100
2020014C7D55E800	11/18/2016	21:43:35	10.9	WV01	0.516	4.432	0
A010014C47F00600	11/30/2017	19:10:22	27.4	WV02	0.577	28.752	9.776
A010014C47F01100	11/30/2017	19:10:21	27.3	WV02	0.576	19.735	0
A010014C47EFAD00	11/30/2017	19:10:23	27.6	WV02	0.578	9.157	100
2020014AA6E4C000	6/16/2018	21:40:44	26.6	WV01	0.605	7.159	0
2020014AA6E47600	6/16/2018	21:39:27	28.1	WV01	0.619	10.122	0
2020014AA6E4B400	6/16/2018	21:40:44	25.5	WV01	0.596	12.609	0
2020014AA6E46500	6/16/2018	21:39:28	28.6	WV01	0.624	35.536	0
2020014AA6E46600	6/16/2018	21:39:29	29	WV01	0.628	11.336	42.39
A010014C4870F600	6/23/2018	18:35:43	26.7	WV02	0.571	8.501	0
A010014C4870DE00	6/23/2018	18:35:41	26.3	WV02	0.567	12.354	67.405
A010014C4870EB00	6/23/2018	18:35:42	26.5	WV02	0.569	36.946	0
2020014AB669FA00	7/22/2018	19:09:19	24.6	WV02	0.552	37.726	0
2020014AB669F900	7/22/2018	19:09:18	24.4	WV02	0.551	11.727	0
2020014AB669F800	7/22/2018	19:09:21	24.7	WV02	0.553	3.604	0
SPOT6_181926300	9/1/2018	19:26.7	9.6	Spot-6	1.5	100	100
Post-Event							
A010014CB01AE900	7/6/2019	19:00:59	14.7	WV03	0.327	0	40.972
A010014CB01D6D00	7/6/2019	19:00:07	17.2	WV03	0.334	8.425	100
A010014CB01C9000	7/6/2019	19:00:08	17.2	WV03	0.334	0	35.575

A010014CB01AE000	7/6/2019	19:00:57	14.6	WV03	0.327	8.418	100
A010014CB020D500	7/13/2019	19:12:01	31.4	WV03	0.411	8.472	0
A010014CAFBE7700	7/13/2019	19:11:02	23.8	WV03	0.361	6.034	0
A010014CB020C100	7/13/2019	19:12:00	30.5	WV03	0.403	7.879	0
A010014BA7372700	7/13/2019	19:11:05	25	WV03	0.368	5.987	0
A010014BA824EE00	7/13/2019	19:12:04	30.7	WV03	0.406	8.163	0
A010014CAFBD6300	7/13/2019	19:11:01	24.8	WV03	0.366	6.079	0
A010014BA733B000	7/14/2019	18:38:53	22.2	WV02	0.537	56.845	100
A010014CAFC8E200	7/14/2019	18:37:32	26.8	WV02	0.574	10.447	0
A010014CAFBE5000	7/14/2019	18:38:48	21.2	WV02	0.529	14.336	83.928
A010014CAFBD3000	7/14/2019	18:38:47	20.4	WV02	0.524	0	67.986
A010014CAFC81400	7/14/2019	18:37:28	29.2	WV02	0.598	2.534	72.313
A010014BA731CA00	7/14/2019	18:37:34	27.6	WV02	0.582	60.051	100
A010014CAFC82200	7/14/2019	18:37:30	28.4	WV02	0.589	14.343	98.307
A010014CAFC84000	7/14/2019	18:37:31	27.6	WV02	0.581	35.314	0
A010014CAFBE5300	7/14/2019	18:38:51	23	WV02	0.542	6.562	0
A010014CAFBE3000	7/14/2019	18:38:50	22.1	WV02	0.535	36.63	0
A010014CB0161B00	7/19/2019	18:54:00	7.1	WV02	0.472	2.362	0
A010014CB0151900	7/19/2019	18:53:00	26.4	WV02	0.566	0.93	0
A010014CB0151B00	7/19/2019	18:52:59	26.1	WV02	0.564	3.259	0
SPOT6_182021500	7/24/2019	18:20:22	8.58	Spot-6	1.5	100	100
A030014BB6903F00	8/2/2019	18:37:55	19.8	WV02	0.519	10.241	0
A030014BB6903F00	8/2/2019	18:39:10	27.7	WV02	0.581	15.192	14.852

A030014BB6903F00	8/2/2019	18:39:12	27.1	WV02	0.576	9.278	0
A030014BB6903F00	8/2/2019	18:37:53	19.8	WV02	0.518	13.914	10.567
A010014CB0232600	9/25/2019	18:48:33	27.8	WV03	0.383	9.535	0
A010014CB01D9D00	9/25/2019	18:47:31	22.1	WV03	0.352	12.69	0
A010014CB023FE00	9/25/2019	18:48:31	27.9	WV03	0.384	12.728	0
A010014CB01D2C00	9/25/2019	18:47:33	22	WV03	0.351	8.68	0
A010014CB01B3500	10/2/2019	18:59:34	32.3	WV03	0.417	2.29	0
A010014CB01B4100	10/2/2019	18:59:33	32.4	WV03	0.418	14.912	74.172
A010014CAFC81900	10/2/2019	18:58:32	4.1	WV03	0.31	12.079	54.752
2020014C7D3D4400	1/21/2020	21:37:44	15.9	WV01	0.534	2.817	0
2020014C3DC44000	1/21/2020	21:37:19	24.7	WV01	0.588	7.239	0
2020014C3DC45B00	1/21/2020	21:37:45	15.6	WV01	0.532	30.517	0
2020014C7D3D7700	1/21/2020	21:37:48	15.1	WV01	0.53	0	30.792
2020014C3DC96A00	1/21/2020	21:37:37	16.6	WV01	0.536	18.406	93.485
2020014C3DC44800	1/21/2020	21:37:44	15.9	WV01	0.534	1.393	0
2020014C3DC44F00	1/21/2020	21:37:47	15.2	WV01	0.53	0	51.333
2020014C3DC94400	1/21/2020	21:37:37	16.6	WV01	0.537	18.89	93.964
2020014C3DC96C00	1/21/2020	21:37:38	15.7	WV01	0.533	3.097	0
2020014C3DC95D00	1/21/2020	21:37:36	17.7	WV01	0.542	8.551	33.124
2020014C7D3D5300	1/21/2020	21:37:45	15.6	WV01	0.532	37.737	0
2020014C3DC42500	1/21/2020	21:37:20	25	WV01	0.591	11.646	0
2020014C3DC46700	1/21/2020	21:37:46	15.4	WV01	0.531	18.005	0
2020014C3DC99E00	1/21/2020	21:37:36	17.6	WV01	0.542	9.177	42.187

2020014C7D3CE70 0	1/21/2020	21:37:3 8	16.1	WV01	0.534	11.394	31.388
2020014C7D3D540 0	1/21/2020	21:37:4 7	15.3	WV01	0.531	6.753	51.271
2020014C3DC91C0 0	1/21/2020	21:37:3 8	15.8	WV01	0.533	3.659	0
2020014C7D3CEF0 0	1/21/2020	21:37:3 6	17.3	WV01	0.54	15.951	93.522